

Alkaloids of the Plant Family Proteaceae

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A brief review of the chemistry of the thirty-two alkaloids so far isolated from proteaceous plants is given, and proposals are put forward concerning the mode of biosynthesis of those of known structure.

THE Proteaceae are considered to be a family of great antiquity¹, with some 60 genera and 1300 species, very largely confined to the southern hemisphere: over half occur in Australia and over a third in southern Africa². They comprise some of the best-known trees and shrubs of these countries, such as the Australian Silky Oak (*Grevillea rostrata*) and Honeysuckles (*Banksia* spp.), and the African Terblanz (*Faurea* spp.), used for timber; also many species such as the Australian Waratahs (*Telopia* spp.) and Hakeas and the South African Sugar Bush (*Protea mellifera*) and Silver Tree (*Leucadendron argentum*) which have been naturalised in other countries as ornamental plants, together with the South American Firebush (*Embothrium coccineum*). Certain of them are also cultivated for their nuts, including the Chile Hazel (*Gevuina avellana*) and the Queensland nut (*Macadomia ternifolia*). Apart from these, a few species occur in the tropical regions of Africa and of both Americas, and in southern and eastern Asia, extending from the south of India to Japan³.

Up to recently, no alkaloids had been isolated from any proteaceous species, although a considerable number had been tested for alkaloids, particularly in Australasia⁴⁻⁶ and South Africa⁹, for the most part with negative results. In 1971, during the course of a survey of Tasmanian endemic plants for alkaloids, a positive test was recorded for the monotypic *Bellenden montana* R. Br.¹⁰. Soon after, the principal alkaloid, bellendine, was isolated and its structure determined¹¹. Since then, alkaloids have been recorded from the New Caledonian *Knightia deplanchei* Viell. ex Brongn. Gris¹², and from another three Australian species: *Agastachys odorata* R. Br.^{13,25} from Tasmania, and *Darlingia darlingiana* (F. Muell), L.A.S. Johnson^{14,15} and *D. ferruginea* J.F. Bailey¹⁴ both from Queensland. A positive test has also been observed on the New Caledonian *K. strobilina*¹⁶, and also on a dried herbarium specimen from the South American *E. coccineum* Forst.¹³, but this has not yet been confirmed on fresh material.

From the incomplete data at present available, little or no pattern can be traced in the rather scattered distribution of alkaloids amongst the Proteaceae. From a consideration of taxonomic data and chromosome numbers, Johnson and Briggs¹⁷ have developed a tentative evolutionary scheme which at the outset divides the Proteaceae into two more or less equally populated

sub-families, Grevilleoideae and Proteoideae. The two Tasmanian alkaloid-containing species, *B. montana* and *A. odorata*, come from separate branches of the latter sub-family, but none of the species closely related to these plants in the scheme have so far been found to contain alkaloids. Furthermore, the Grevilleoideae contain the alkaloid-bearing New Caledonian *Knightia* spp. and the two *Darlingia* spp. related to them, but on the other hand, no alkaloids could be detected in the even more closely related *K. excelsa* from New Zealand⁶.

The family most closely related to the Proteaceae is the Thymelaeaceae³, of which a few members have been recorded as giving positive alkaloid tests,^{18,19} but no information is available on the types of alkaloids which may be present.

The alkaloids so far isolated from the Proteaceae can be grouped under six headings depending on their structures and substitution patterns:

Pyrrolidines

(I) Dehydrodarlinine (*D. darlingiana*)²⁰,
m.p. 42-44°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 64^\circ$ (CHCl₃)

The structure was deduced from spectroscopic data and confirmed by synthesis of the racemic base by condensation of ($\pm$) hygrine (II) with benzaldehyde.

The absolute stereochemistry of dehydrodarlinine is not yet known, but the enantiomeric configuration to

(III) Darlinine (*D. darlingiana*)²⁰ m.p. 59-61°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 75^\circ$
(CHCl₃)

(IV) Epidarlinine (*D. darlingiana*)₂₀ m.p. 66-68°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 59^\circ$
(CHCl₃)

naturally-occurring hygrine has been tentatively assigned to it and to the other pyrrolidine bases (III)-(IX) isolated from *D. darlingiana*, from a comparison of their rotations with those of hygrine and of the corresponding epimeric secondary alcohols formed on reduction.

The epimeric bases darlinine and epidarlinine accompany dehydrodarlinine and can be formed from it by borohydride reduction. Their relative stereochemistries were established by comparison of their R_f values and nmr spectra with those of darlingianine (VI) and its synthetic epimer.

(V) Dehydrodarlingianine (*D. darlingiana*)²⁰, m.p. 54-55°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 53^\circ$ (CHCl₃)

From spectroscopic data this yellow base has an analogous structure to dehydrodarlinine, with an extra conjugated *trans* olefinic group. The structure was confirmed by synthesis of the racemic base by condensation of hygrine (II) and cinnamaldehyde.

(VI) Darlingianine (*D. darlingiana*)^{15,20}, m. p. 93-94°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 62^\circ$ (CHCl₃)

The structure of darlingianine was deduced from spectroscopic data; the base has been synthesised by reduction of dehydrodarlingianine and the structure has been confirmed by X-ray crystallographic analysis, from which the relative stereochemistry has also been deduced. The absolute configuration is not yet known, but has been provisionally assigned on the same basis as that of dehydrodarlinine (I).

(VII) Dihydrodarlingianine (*D. darlingiana*)²⁰, m.p. 72-74°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 34^\circ$ (CHCl₃)

(VIII) Tetrahydrodarlingianine (*D. darlingiana*)²⁰, oil, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 22^\circ$ (CHCl₃); picrate, m.p. 178-181°

The structures of these bases (VII) and (VIII) were deduced from spectroscopic evidence and confirmed by controlled catalytic hydrogenation of darlingianine.

(IX)

(IX) Isodarlingianine (*D. darlingiana*)²⁰ m.p. 50-52°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 47^\circ$ (CHCl₃)

This base was assigned an isomeric structure to darlingianine from spectroscopic data, with one double bond *cis* instead of *trans*.

Monosubstituted Tropanes

The structure of (X) deduced from spectroscopic data has been confirmed by a synthesis of the enantiomeric base, starting from the acid chloride of anhydroecgonine (XI). Since the absolute stereochemistry of anhydroecgonine is known from its relationship to cocaine, this fixes the absolute configuration of naturally-occurring ferruginine as (X).

(X) Ferruginine (*D. ferruginea* and *D. darlingiana*)²⁰ oil, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 37^\circ$ (CHCl₃); picrate, m.p. 161-163°

(XII) Ferrugine (*D. ferruginea*)^{14,20}, m.p. 101-102°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 55^\circ$ (CHCl₃); picrate, m.p. 192-194°

The structure and relative stereochemistry of ferruginine followed from spectroscopic data; in particular, the configuration at C₂ was assigned on the basis of the ¹³C NMR spectrum: the C₄ resonance was only slightly shifted from the value recorded for unsubstituted tropane²², in accord with the negligible γ -effect exerted by equatorial substituents on conformationally-fixed six-membered rings.

3,6-Disubstituted Tropanes

The structure and relative stereochemistry deduced for (XIII) were confirmed by synthesis by standard methods; it proved identical with an alkaloid isolated from *Datura sanguinea*²³.

The structure of the minor base (XIV) was deduced by spectroscopy and confirmed by synthesis.

The isomeric alkaloids (XV) and (XVI) occur together and could not be separated. Their properties, including spectroscopic data, are almost identical; however, they showed small but distinct differences in the chemical shifts of the isopropyl groups in the two cases. Equal amounts of the two bases prepared synthetically by standard means and combined gave an nmr spectrum superimposable on that of the naturally-occurring mixed bases.

(XIII) 6 β -Acetoxy-3 α -tigloyloxytropane (*A. odorata*)^{13,25} oil, $[\alpha]_D^{19} -14^\circ$ (CHCl₃); picrate, m.p. 180-182°

(XIV) R=H, R₁=COCH₃, 6 β -Hydroxy-3 α -acetoxytropane (*B. montana*)¹⁸, oil, $[\alpha]_D^{19} -29^\circ$ (CHCl₃); picrate, m.p. 182-184°

(XV) R=COCH₃; R₁=(CH₂)₂CHCO, 6 β -Acetoxy-3 α -isobutoxytropane (*B. Montana*)¹⁸

(XVI) R=(CH₂)₂CHCO; R₁=COCH₃, 6 β -Isobutoxy-3 α -acetoxytropane (*B. montana*)¹⁸

2,3-Disubstituted Tropanes

The structures of the racemic oily bases (XVII) and (XVIII), deduced from spectroscopic data, were confirmed by syntheses which involved condensation of benzaldehyde with tropanone as the first step. Their stereochemistries have been determined by ¹³C NMR spectroscopy.

(XVII) Alkaloid A oil, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$ and (XVIII) Alkaloid B, oil, $[\alpha]_D + 0^\circ$ (*K. deplanchei*)^{13,21,22}

(XIX) Alkaloid F₂, (*D. ferruginea*)²⁰, m.p. 136-138°, $[\alpha]_D^{19} + 28^\circ$ (CHCl₃)

The base (XIX) has been assigned the structure shown above on the basis of spectroscopic data. The configurations of the 2- and 3-substituents are not yet known.

Trisubstituted Tropanes

The structure of the racemic base (XX) was deduced from spectroscopic data; in particular, the configuration at C₆ was apparent from the dramatic shift in field of the C₂, C₄, and N-methyl carbons on hydrolysis of the 6 α -acyl group. This was interpreted as being due to an inversion of the N-methyl group as a result of H-bonding with the 6-OH group.

The structure of (XXI) was deduced from spectroscopic data. On hydrolysis, it gave a glycol isomeric with the hydrolysis product from alkaloid C (XX); on the other hand, the C₁ carbons of the two glycols have different chemical shifts due to the β -effect of the C₆ hydroxy in the former case. Alkaloid D shows the same high-field N-methyl carbon resonance as the glycol derived from alkaloid C, showing that the 7-oxy function must be β -oriented.

(XX) Alkaloid C (*K. deplanchei*)^{12,22}, m.p. 168-170°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$

(XXI) Alkaloid D (*K. deplanchei*)^{12,22}, m.p. 174-175°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$

(XXII) Alkaloid F (*K. deplanchei*)^{12,22}, m.p. 164-167°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$

(XXIII) Alkaloid E (*K. deplanchei*)²²

The structure and stereochemistry of (XXII) was assigned from similar considerations of spectroscopic evidence to those of alkaloids C and D.

The above tentative structure (XXII) has been proposed for this oily racemic Alkaloid E, but the stereochemistry has not yet been determined.

Pyranotropones

Bellendine (XXIV) was the first proteaceous alkaloid to be isolated; its structure was determined by X-ray crystallography and it has been synthesised by C-acylation of tropanone followed by closure of the pyrone ring. The absolute stereochemistry of bellendine and of the other pyranotropone alkaloids has not yet been determined.

The structure of isobellendine (XXV) was proved by a comparison of its spectra with those of the isomeric bellendine and was confirmed by a synthesis along the same lines as for the latter alkaloid.

Darlingine (XXIV) is the most widespread of the proteaceous alkaloids. Its structure, homologous with those of bellendine and isobellendine, was deduced by comparison of the spectra of the three bases and was confirmed by synthesis.

The structure and relative stereochemistry of (XXVII) were determined from spectroscopic data; in

particular, the *cis endo* fusion of the tropane and pyrone rings was deduced from the couplings of the protons attached at the ring junction with one another and with the protons on the adjacent carbons. The base has been synthesised in low yield by the same general method used for the above pyranotropanes.

This minor alkaloid (XXVIII) from spectroscopic data has a structure analogous to that of (XXVII). However, the two bases differ in the method of ring junction, which has not yet been fixed in the case of 5,11-dihydrodarlingine (XXVIII).

- (XXIV) Bellendine (*B. montana*)^{10,11,24}, m.p. 162°, $[\alpha]_D^{19} + 168^\circ$ (CHCl₃)
- (XXV) Isobellendine (*B. montana*)^{13,25}, m.p. 114°, $[\alpha]_D^{19} + 143^\circ$ (CHCl₃)
- (XXVI) Darlingine (*D. darlingiana*, *D. ferruginea*, and *B. montana*)^{13,14,25}, m.p. 162-163°, $[\alpha]_D^{19} + 104^\circ$ (CHCl₃)
- (XXVII) 5,11-Dihydroisobellendine (*B. montana*)^{13,25}, oil, $[\alpha]_D^{19} - 53^\circ$ (CHCl₃), picrate, m.p. 172-174°
- (XXVIII) 5,11-Dihydrodarlingine (*D. darlingiana*)¹³, oil, $[\alpha]_D^{19} + 37^\circ$ (CHCl₃), picrate, m.p. 165-168°
- (XXIX) 2,3-Dihydrobellendine (*B. montana*)¹³, oil, $[\alpha]_D^{19} + 59^\circ$ (CHCl₃), picrate, m.p. 188-190°
- (XXX) 2,3-Dihydrodarlingine (*B. montana*)¹³, oil, $[\alpha]_D^{19} + 68^\circ$ (CHCl₃), picrate, m.p. 191-194°

Spectroscopic data indicate that the minor alkaloid (XXIX) is an isomer of 5, 11-dihydroisobellendine

(XXVII), with the C-methyl group on an aliphatic methine carbon adjacent to the carbonyl group, consistent with the above structure.

The minor alkaloid (XXX) is an isomer of 5,11-dihydrodarlingine, with the double bond located at the ring junction, as shown by spectroscopic data.

Alkaloids of unknown or incompletely known structure

(XXXI) Alkaloid B₂, (*B. montana*)¹³ oil, M.W. 249.

Spectroscopic data suggest that it has a tropane nucleus, with two carbonyls, one conjugated.

(XXXII) Alkaloid A₂, (*A. odorata*)^{13,25} oil, C₁₅H₁₇NO₃

Spectroscopic data are consistent with structure (XXXII). However, its occurrence in the plant has not yet been confirmed and it may be an artefact produced during work-up and purification.

(XXXIII) Alkaloid B₂ (*B. montana*)¹³ C₁₅H₂₁NO₃, m.p. 186-187°

Spectroscopic data show the presence of two carbonyl groups and indicate that B₂ is not a tropane alkaloid.

Possible mode of biosynthesis of proteaceous alkaloids

No biosynthetic studies have been carried out to date on proteaceous plants; however, from the range of alkaloid types so far isolated, a pattern has emerged which permits a possible biogenetic pathway to be postulated as a preliminary to labelling experiments.

The proteaceous alkaloids so far found, excluding those whose structures are still unknown, are substituted pyrrolidines and tropanes. They are thus structurally analogous to alkaloid types found in plant families which are phylogenetically remote from the Proteaceae, such as the Solanaceae and Erythroxylaceae. The biosyntheses of several alkaloids belonging to these families have been investigated in some detail²⁷ and it has been established that the pyrrolidine ring of such bases as hygrine (II) arises from the amino acid ornithine and the side chain from two acetate units; in the tropane alkaloid, this acetate chain cyclises with the pyrrolidine residue to form a 6-membered ring. As a working hypothesis capable of being tested subsequently by labelling experiments, it is reasonable to suppose that the alkaloids of the Proteaceae are formed in an analogous fashion, although a pathway different from this certainly cannot be ruled out without the support of such experiments.

SCHEME 1

A general scheme of biogenesis of the proteaceous alkaloids could then be postulated as shown in Scheme 1. The proposed scheme raises a number of questions for future study: for instance, (I) and its analogues could be formed from a cinnamate and an acetate unit instead of benzoate and two acetate units and (V) and its analogues could arise from a cinnamate and two acetate units; moreover, the biosynthesis of bellendine (XXIV) could take place by methylation of isobellendine (XXV) to darlingine (XXVI) followed by demethylation, or alternatively from isobellendine directly by the shift of a methyl group.

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